

CONSTITUTIVE MODELING OF POLYMERIC MATRIX UNDER MULTI-AXIAL STATIC AND DYNAMIC LOADING

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1. General Introduction

Recent and ongoing research in fiber reinforced polymer composites has shown that there is a significant rate effect on the resin dominated stiffness and strength properties of these materials [1, 2]. Fabrication and testing of these composites is costly due to the expense of the material itself, and its anisotropic behavior that requires time consuming multi-axial testing. In the case of carbon/epoxy composites, the fiber itself shows no rate dependence in its mechanical response. This suggests that all of the rate effects on the composite can be traced to the matrix. Since the polymer matrix is basically isotropic, a much less costly evaluation of a composite can be achieved by characterizing the bulk matrix at various strain rates.

The constitutive and strain rate behavior of epoxies under various loading conditions has been studied by many researchers [3-13]. Some studies focus on characterization of the resin at various rates [3, 4]. Many investigators have focused on viscoelastic analysis and the determination of shift factors used in temperature-time superposition modeling [5-8]. Some have attempted to link the monomer structure to the bulk properties [9]. Goldberg et al. have published works on both testing various resins under multiaxial conditions at various rates as well as modeling with a state variable approach [10-13]. The objective of this study was to characterize a matrix resin under multi-axial loading at different strain rates and develop a general three-dimensional elasto-viscoplastic model that incorporates rate effects including dilatational and deviatoric states

of stress. Emphasis was placed on development of a relatively simple model that would not require extensive testing for evaluation of a given matrix.

2. Material Characterization

2.1 Material and Specimen Preparation

The polymer matrix investigated is a high stiffness, high strength epoxy (3501-6) commonly used in composites. It has a highly crosslinked structure that provides stiffness and strength but also reduces its ductility. The B-staged resin is normally stored in a freezer. The partially cured and frozen resin was chipped out, weighed, and placed in the mold. A small amount of acetone was added to reduce the resin viscosity and facilitate casting of the partially cured resin into the mold. The temperature was raised at a rate of 2 C/min up to 120 °C, and held at that level for one hour. During this stage the resin viscosity was low and vacuum was drawn at 760 mm of Hg to remove any air that may have been trapped and to boil off any acetone that might remain in the resin. Subsequently, the vacuum was removed and air was slowly bled back into the mold. For large volumes of resin, the amount of solvent is restricted to prevent the acetone from igniting as it boils off during the exothermic stage of the cure. The material was cast into closed molds to produce thin (3 mm) plates for tensile coupons, thick blocks for prismatic compression coupons, and thin-wall cylinders for specimens to be tested under torsion and combinations of torsion and axial tension or compression. In casting the cylinders, an

aluminum tube was used as the mold with a Teflon rod inserted as the core.

The geometry and dimensions of the specimens used are shown in Figure 1. Specimens for uniaxial tensile testing were thin dogbone coupons with a gage section of 12.7 mm x 50.8 mm machined from 3 mm thick sheets. Uniaxial compressive tests were conducted on thick prismatic coupons 12.7 mm long with a cross section of 7.62 mm x 8.89 mm. It was important to maintain an aspect ratio of around 1.5 because lower aspect ratios would lead to end effects producing a multi-axial stress state that would result in a higher apparent modulus and critical stress. A higher aspect ratio would cause buckling of the specimen and a decrease in the critical stress. Aspect ratios from 0.125 to 2.7 were tested and it was found that low aspect ratios yielded stiffness values approaching the plane strain stiffness value (C_{11}) and the higher aspect ratios yielded the Young's modulus E of the material. An aspect ratio of 1.5 was chosen for the determination of Young's modulus E (Figure 2). Tests under pure shear and combinations of shear and normal tensile or compressive stress were conducted on thin-wall cylindrical specimens. Since the resin used has a shear strength higher than that of available bonding epoxies, the cylindrical specimens were designed and machined with enlarged ends and fillets as shown in Fig. 1. The cylinders were machined using a lathe to produce a 1.27 mm wall thickness in the gage section and a fillet radius of 11.4 mm. The cylindrical specimens were mounted on a steel post used to apply compression and torsion.

2.2 Testing

Experiments were conducted at various strain rates ranging from 10^{-5} to 1500 s^{-1} . Lower rate experiments at less than 1 s^{-1} were conducted in a servo-hydraulic testing machine while the higher rate tests were conducted in a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar system. Tension and pure shear tests at lower rates, 10^{-4} to 1 s^{-1} , did not show much rate dependence in stress-strain behavior. Similarly, the brittle failure under tensile loading did not show much variation (Figure 3). The rate effect was much more pronounced under uniaxial compression.

Dynamic testing at high strain rates was conducted in a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) system. Typically, in such tests, either polymeric bars such as polycarbonate or metallic bars such as steel or aluminum are used. However, the resin tested was stiffer and stronger than most polymers and it would damage the ends of the bars during testing. For metallic bars, not only is there a very large impedance mismatch, the resin reaches ultimate failure at strains above 20%. The wave speed in metallic bars is very high and the length of the bars needed to produce a long enough stress pulse to achieve the required ultimate strain was impractical. A compromise was reached with composite (G-10) rods made of stacked layers of woven glass/epoxy. The impedance of the bars was not too different from that of the resin, a fact which allowed stress equilibration within the specimen to occur much sooner than in the steel or aluminum Hopkinson bar systems (Figure 4). The wave speed in the composite bars was much lower than that in the metallic bars, so that a 1.83 m incident bar was sufficient to capture most of the resin behavior. Because the glass fibers in the G-10 bars are oriented along the axis of the bar, the stress wave did not show much dispersion or attenuation, and thus, there was no need for a more complex viscoelastic analysis of the signals. The only concern was the lack of axisymmetry in the rods, but no significant difference was observed in the propagating pulse monitored by strain gages along the principal planes of the bar cross section.

2.3 Stress-Strain Behavior

Stress-strain curves were obtained over a wide range of strain rates. The compressive stress-strain curves shown in Figure 5 have the same overall form and share many key features. They exhibit a linear elastic region up to the yield point, followed by a plastic region up to a critical point of material instability, the "critical stress." Next, follows a softening plateau reaching a local minimum, followed by strain hardening. All curves share the same initial modulus. The rate dependence appears only in the nonlinear regime. The characteristic features of the curves expand radially from the origin with increasing strain rate as highlighted in Fig. 5.

These characteristic properties vary linearly with the logarithm of strain rate as shown in Figure 6. The resulting rate dependence can be expressed as

$$P(\dot{\varepsilon}) = P(\dot{\varepsilon}_0) \left[m \log_{10} \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} + 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

where $P(\dot{\varepsilon})$ is the rate dependent property, $P(\dot{\varepsilon}_0)$ is the property at the reference strain rate (10^{-4} s^{-1} in this case) and m is the slope of the linear logarithmic relation (0.096 in this case). Using this relation, the stress-strain curves were transformed into one master curve at the reference strain rate as shown in Fig. 7.

3. Constitutive Modeling of Polymeric Matrix

3.1 Potential Function

Most models for polymers are expressed in stress space. However, because of the softening and subsequent hardening behavior of the stress-strain curves, the strain dependence of the stress is not unique. For this reason an approach formulated in strain space was used. It is also valuable to break up the constitutive response into two regions, one pre-critical stress and the other post-critical stress region. Here the emphasis was placed on the material behavior in the pre-critical stress region. In a general nonlinear elastic-plastic stress-strain response shown in Figure 8, the total stress increment can be decomposed into an elastic part and a plastic part as

$$d\sigma_i = d\sigma_i^e - d\sigma_i^p \quad (2)$$

The elastic stress increment is linearly related to the total strain increment by the stiffness C_{ij} as

$$d\sigma_i^e = C_{ij} d\varepsilon_j \quad (3)$$

The plastic stress increment is related to a potential (or loading) function through the associated flow rule and normality rule as follows:

$$d\sigma_i^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_i} \quad (4)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$; f is a plastic potential function; and $d\lambda$ is a scalar function of proportionality. The constitutive model sought is obtained from the plastic potential and scalar functions.

A plastic potential function was proposed based on a modified Drucker-Prager [14] yield criterion.

The proposed model describes the multi-axial stress-strain behavior and accounts for coupling of deviatoric and dilatational deformation and the sign of the normal stress (tension or compression). The potential function in strain space is expressed as:

$$f = \left\{ a \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + 6(\varepsilon_4^2 + \varepsilon_5^2 + \varepsilon_6^2) \right] + a_1 (\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3)^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} + b(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3) = \bar{\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

where a , a_1 , and b are plastic anisotropy numbers, and $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is the effective strain that contributes to plastic work. All strains are elastic-plastic strains defined as:

$$\varepsilon_i = \left\langle \varepsilon_i^t - \varepsilon_i^y \right\rangle \quad (6)$$

where ε_i^t is the total strain and ε_i^y is the yield strain. For this material, under most loading conditions the yield strain is effectively zero as the material shows nonlinear behavior from the start. However, under compression, the normal strain is linear up to a certain point. This region does not contribute to the plastic work performed, as shown in Figure 8. For the master compressive stress-strain curve, this normal yield strain is 1.6%.

3.2 Constitutive Relations

The incremental plastic strain energy per unit volume is given in terms of the effective plastic stress as

$$dW_p = \varepsilon_i d\sigma_i^p = \bar{\varepsilon} d\bar{\sigma}^p \quad (7)$$

Where $d\bar{\sigma}^p$ is the increment in effective plastic stress. Replacing the plastic stress increment with the gradient of the potential function by the flow rule of Eq. (4) we obtain,

$$\bar{\varepsilon} d\bar{\sigma}^p = \varepsilon_i \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_i} d\lambda = \bar{\varepsilon} d\lambda \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the scalar function of proportionality is given by

$$d\lambda = d\bar{\sigma}^p \quad (9)$$

Assuming a power law relationship between the effective plastic stress and effective strain as

$$\bar{\sigma}^p = A \bar{\varepsilon}^n \quad (10)$$

we obtain the following expression for the scalar function of proportionality:

$$d\lambda = nA(\bar{\varepsilon})^{n-1} d\bar{\varepsilon} \quad (11)$$

The incremental effective strain, as defined in Eq. (4), is

$$d\bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_j} d\varepsilon_j \quad (12)$$

Using Eqs. (2-4), and (9-12) we obtain the constitutive elasto/viscoplastic model for the total stress and strain increments as

$$d\sigma_i = \left[C_{ij} - nA\bar{\varepsilon}^{n-1} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_i} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_j} \right] d\varepsilon_j \quad (13)$$

In order to account for the rate effect, compressive normal stresses and strains must be transformed to the reference strain rate using Eq. (1).

3.2 Model Parameters

The constitutive law is expressed in terms of three parameters associated with the potential function, a , a_v , and b , and two power law parameters, A and n , which relate the effective plastic stress with the effective strain. However, the three parameters in the potential function are not independent. They are used to transform any given state of strain into an effective strain. For this reason, the potential function can be normalized by one of the parameters, or any loading condition can be chosen to represent a strain equivalent to the effective strain. Since the pure shear and tension tests produced relatively low strains before failure, the uniaxial compression test was chosen to yield the effective strain. In this test, ε_1 denotes the axial strain, the shear strains being zero, and

$$\varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon_3 = -\nu\varepsilon_1 \quad (14)$$

Substituting these into the potential function, we obtain the following relation

$$f = \varepsilon_1 \left\{ \left[2a(1+\nu)^2 + a_v(1-2\nu)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - b(1-2\nu) \right\} = \bar{\varepsilon} \quad (15)$$

Since, under uniaxial compression, the axial strain is chosen as the effective strain

$$\left[2a(1+\nu)^2 + a_v(1-2\nu)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - b(1-2\nu) = 1 \quad (16)$$

This provides a direct relation for the sign dependent dilatational constant b in terms of a , and a_v

$$b = \frac{\left[2a(1+\nu)^2 + a_v(1-2\nu)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1}{(1-2\nu)} \quad (17)$$

A direct expression for parameter a can be found by comparing the pure shear and uniaxial compression tests at the critical point. At the critical point the slope of the stress-strain curve is zero

$$\frac{d\sigma_1}{d\varepsilon_1} = \frac{d\tau_6}{d\varepsilon_6} = 0 \quad (18)$$

Using the incremental constitutive law in Eq. (13) and Eq. (18), we obtain the following relations

$$C_{11} = nA\bar{\varepsilon}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_1} \right)^2 \frac{(1-\nu)}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (19)$$

$$C_{66} = nA\bar{\varepsilon}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_6} \right)^2 \quad (20)$$

By definition, from Eq. (15) for a uniaxial compression test,

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_1} = 1 \quad (21)$$

and for a pure shear test

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_6} = (6a)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (22)$$

Thus, by combining Eqs. (19-22), an expression for parameter a can be found

$$a = \frac{C_{66}(1-\nu)}{6C_{11}(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} = \frac{G}{3E} = 0.123 \quad (23)$$

The final potential function parameter, a_v , can be found from the tension tests. It is sensitive to the value of a_v , so that it is not difficult to fit it to the remaining data. The parameter a_v was found to have a value of 5.8. The power law parameters A and n were determined by using the critical point under uniaxial compression. Equation (19) can be rewritten in terms of the product nA at the critical point $\bar{\varepsilon}_c$

$$nA = C_{11} \bar{\varepsilon}_c^{1-n} \frac{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}{(1-\nu)} = E \bar{\varepsilon}_c^{1-n} \quad (24)$$

Then, substituting in the total strain value from Eq. (6) we obtain

$$nA = E \left(\varepsilon_{1c}^t - \varepsilon_1^y \right)^{1-n} \quad (25)$$

The critical stress is then found by integrating the incremental constitutive law, Eq. (13), from zero to the total critical strain, ε_c^t

$$\sigma_{1c} = \int_0^{\varepsilon_{1c}^t} E - nA \left(\varepsilon_1^t - \varepsilon_1^y \right)^{n-1} d\varepsilon_1 \quad (26)$$

Substituting in Eq. (25) and integrating, we obtain an expression for n

$$n = \frac{E(\varepsilon_{1c}^t - \varepsilon_1^y)}{E\varepsilon_{1c}^t - \sigma_{1c}} \quad (27)$$

Finally, rearranging Eq. (25) provides an expression for A

$$A = \frac{E(\varepsilon_{1c}^t - \varepsilon_1^y)^{1-n}}{n} \quad (28)$$

All five model parameters can be obtained using the basic elastic constants of the material, the characteristic properties of the stress-strain curve (yield strain ε_1^y , critical strain, ε_{1c} , and critical stress, σ_c) and by fitting the stress-strain curve under uniaxial tension.

Using these parameters and the experimental data from uniaxial tension and compression, pure shear, and combined loading tests, as well as the transformed stress-strain curves at various strain rates, all of the effective strain-effective plastic stress curves collapse into a master curve as shown in Figure 9. The heavy solid black curve is the power law approximation for this relationship obtained as discussed above.

3.3 Model Validation

The model was formulated using uniaxial tension and compression and pure shear tests at different strain rates. Figures 10 and 11, show that the predictions of the proposed constitutive model are in excellent agreement with experimental results.

All of the tests and model predictions reported thus far have been uniaxial stress or strain tests, but the model is valid for combined loadings as well. Two minor changes must be made to the model derivation described above. First, to account for the rate effect, the strain rates used in Eq. (1) must be converted to effective strain rates. This extends the the model to include strain rate effects under multi-axial states of stress and strain.

$$P(\bar{\dot{\varepsilon}}) = P(\bar{\dot{\varepsilon}}_0) \left[m \log_{10} \frac{\bar{\dot{\varepsilon}}}{\bar{\dot{\varepsilon}}_0} + 1 \right] \quad (29)$$

This change does not affect any of the results presented earlier, applied only for uniaxial compression tests. Under those loading conditions, the effective strain is equivalent to the axial strain. The other modification is that the yield strain used

before is a principal yield strain and it must be changed to the axial yield strain under the given loading condition.

For combined loading tests, the same thin wall cylindrical specimen and procedure were used as for the pure shear tests. The servo-hydraulic testing machine was controlled to apply a constant displacement rate in compression and rotation to provide the desired loading condition. For these tests, the compressive strain rate was specified to be 75% of the shear strain rate. This would provide a loading condition that would exhibit nonlinearity in both compression and shear. Tests were conducted at two different strain rates to confirm that the model could account for rate effects under combined loading. Figure 12 shows excellent agreement between predictions of the proposed constitutive model and experimental results under combined compression and shear at two strain rates.

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Fig.1. Specimen geometries and dimensions

- (a) Tensile, (b) Compressive, (c) Shear and combined stress specimens

Fig. 2. Effect of aspect ratio on compressive response

Fig. 3 Tension and shear stress-strain curves at two strain rates

Fig. 4. Stresses at ends of resin specimen for different Hopkinson bar materials

Fig. 5. Compressive stress-strain curves at various strain rates showing radial alignment of characteristic features

Fig. 6. Variation of normalized critical and yield stresses with strain rate

Fig. 7. Master compressive stress-strain curve at reference strain rate

Fig. 8. Definition of plastic stress and plastic work

Fig. 9. Collapsed curves of tension, shear, compression and combined loadings at various strain rates with power law model

Fig.10. Comparison between model predictions and experimental results for (a) uniaxial tension and (b) shear tests

Fig. 11. Comparison between model predictions and experimental results for uniaxial compression tests at different strain rates

Fig. 12. Combined loading experiments and model predictions at different strain rates

Table 1 Model parameters

Parameter	Value
a	0.123
a_v	5.4
b	-0.108
A	20123
n	1.68